

Surface geology of Arsinoes Chaos: morphological and spectral affinities across Chaotic terrains on Mars

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We are mapping surface units on Arsinoes Chaos (Mars) based on morphological observations from CTX and HiRISE experiments, as well as through spectral analyses of CRISM data. Strong analogies in the depositional, erosional and collapse history suggest that the processes acting in Arsinoes Chaos may be the same responsible for the formation of other Chaotic terrains such as Aram Chaos [1] and Aureum Chaos [2]. Aram and Aureum Chaos are characterized by a basaltic bedrock disrupted into kilometeric polygonal blocks and knobs, locally carved by outflow channels and stratigraphically underlying sedimentary units rich in sulfates. Several interpretations were proposed in literature for the origin of such features, as summarized by [3]; the common point between all the scenarios is the occurrence of a catastrophic collapse and consequent outflow. In Arsinoes Chaos, in addition to the typical bedrock disruption in polygonal blocks and knobs, also the layered sedimentary fill displays morphological affinities with those occurring in the other Chaotic terrains. If the spectral analyses will confirm the mineralogical analogy between Arsinoes, Aram and Aureum Chaos, we expect to observe the spectral signature of hydrated minerals (such as sulfates), plus possibly hematite. The depositional environment inferred for the sedimentary units in Aram Chaos [e.g. 1] is water-rich with possible evidences of hydrothermal or diagenetic processes. We are investigating the possible regional correlations between Chaotic terrains, as well as the possible variability of tectonic and depositional processes within and across them.

References:

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